

Research Article

Soil Detective Adventure Kit

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Abstract: *The Soil Detective Adventure Kit is an interactive educational tool that is intended to facilitate the exploration and comprehension of soil science by students through exploratory learning and hands-on activities. This kit is designed to introduce the fundamental concepts of soil composition, to learners of varying ages but specifically targeting pre-school kids. By simulating real-world experiments and investigations, students take on the role of "soil detectives" as they investigate various soil samples to observe the different soil horizons, such as the organic-rich O-horizon, the nutrient-rich A-horizon (topsoil), the B-horizon (subsoil), and the weathered C-horizon and the unweathered R-horizon. The kit comes with all the necessary equipment including guidebook, tools for the soil horizon and pre-packaged soil samples of various types, such as organic matter soil, sand, clay, parent rock and pebbles, to provide a full sensory learning experience for kids. The Soil Detective Adventure Kit equips young students to become "junior scientists" by offering all the necessary materials for an experiential journey into the world of soil, all while encouraging curiosity. The package provides a fun yet instructive experience designed for young student and is perfect for use in homes, classrooms, and outdoor environments.*

Keywords: Soil Detective Adventure kit; soil horizon; inquiry-based learning.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The *Soil Detective Adventure Kit* is designed to introduce primary school children to the fascinating world of soil through playful, hands-on activities. Soil is a fundamental part of the earth's ecosystem, supporting plant growth, recycling nutrients, and maintaining biodiversity (Brady & Weil, 2016). With this kit, young learners are encouraged to explore different soil types such as sand, clay, and loam using simple, child-friendly tools and guided activities.

Research highlights the importance of early science education for fostering cognitive development and a sense of environmental stewardship in children. By engaging in tactile activities that focus on soil's texture, colour, and organic content, children can develop a better understanding of how soil supports life on earth. The *Soil Detective Adventure Kit* not only provides pre-packaged soil samples and all necessary tools but also introduces the concept of soil layers (or horizons), giving

children a foundational understanding of how soils form and function in nature. This kit offers an engaging way for kids to connect with nature, whether used in classrooms, homes, or outdoor settings. By making learning both fun and interactive, the *Soil Detective Adventure Kit* helps cultivate curiosity and a lifelong appreciation for science and the environment.

The primary objective of this product is to assist Malaysia's Ministry of Education in advancing technical and vocational education and training (TVET). The initial concept was to develop a science-related agricultural product. Upon identifying deficiencies in the scientific curriculum, particularly within the agriculture courses of TVET, the decision was made to concentrate on soil science. This adventure kit can fit into different topics for both primary and secondary school levels, but this kit was curated to focus on primary schools because it's important to build understanding at a young age to nurture the curiosity based on the hands-on activities.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

The Soil Adventure Kit was developed in 2022, initiated with a survey aimed at correlating the topic with the TVET syllabus, finding deficiencies in the science curriculum, and connecting it with primary, and secondary education levels. It was then proceeded with the initial phase of product development began, including idea generation, sketching, and design. By 2023, the product design led to the development of the first prototype of the "Soil Detectives Adventure Kit," which won a bronze medal in the Pitching (Educator) category at the International e-Content Development Competition 2023, held in August 2023. In March 2024, the second prototype was developed, converting the product into a printed gable box format with best pre-tested material suitable for kids' usage. In October 2024, the project participated in the International Learning Innovation Competition 2024 (PIP 2024) event, and managed to secure silver medal. The Soil Detective Adventure Kit already granted the Copyright by MyIPO on October 2024.

3. FINDINGS

3.1 Curriculum Gaps Identified

A survey conducted in 2022 identified significant gaps in the science curriculum, particularly regarding the lack of hands-on learning opportunities related to environmental science and soil education. This gap limits students' exposure to practical, real-world applications of science, which is crucial for aligning with the TVET syllabus. Addressing these gaps is essential to enhance the curriculum's effectiveness and to ensure that students develop practical skills along with theoretical knowledge.

3.2 Prototype Development and Feedback

In August 2023, the initial prototype of the "Soil Detectives Adventure Kit" was developed. This product aimed to address the identified gaps by offering an interactive, hands-on learning experience in soil science. Feedback from educators and students was overwhelmingly positive, with particular praise for its engaging content and educational value. This was further validated when the prototype won a bronze medal in the Pitching (Educator) category at the International e-Content Development Competition in June 2023 (International e-Content Development Competition, 2023).

3.3 Second Prototype and Educational Enhancement

By March 2024, a second prototype was developed, incorporating a printed gable box design to enhance durability and presentation. This iteration made the product more user-friendly and accessible, particularly for younger students, improving engagement and comprehension. The updates to the content and format were designed to make the learning experience smoother and more effective if it been used in classroom settings.

Figure 1. Final Product Box with Dimension

3.4 International Learning Innovation Competition 2024 (PIP 2024) and ISBN Registration

In October 2024, the project participated in the PIP 2024 event, marking an important milestone for the "Soil Detectives Adventure Kit." Additionally, the adventure book will further register to receive an ISBN, formalizing the product's availability for wider distribution in educational markets. This step ensures that the product is ready for larger-scale implementation across schools.

Figure 2. Component in the Soil Adventure Kit Box

3.5 Trial and Field Testing

Initial product trials were conducted at selected schools in 2024, revealing positive outcomes. Students showed increased engagement with the adventure-based learning model, while teachers reported that the kit encouraged curiosity and critical thinking in students. The feedback suggested that the "Soil Detectives Adventure Kit" had significant potential for incorporation into the regular science curriculum.

Figure 3. Field Testing of the Final Product

4. DISCUSSION

The findings from this project underscore the importance of addressing gaps in the current science curriculum, particularly in providing more interactive and practical learning tools. The Soil Detectives Adventure Kit was developed in response to these gaps and has proven to be an effective solution for enhancing students' understanding of soil science and environmental education. By bridging the gaps between primary, and secondary levels, students are better equipped to grasp complex scientific concepts and apply them in practical settings. The initial development of the "Soil Detectives Adventure Kit" and its subsequent recognition at the International e-Content Development Competition in 2023 demonstrate the product's potential to address these educational challenges. The feedback from educators and students has been overwhelmingly positive, with many highlighting the kit's ability to make learning fun and engaging. The second prototype, developed in 2024, reflects the ongoing effort to refine the product and make it more classroom-friendly. The shift to a printed gable box format, along with improved visuals and content, has enhanced the kit's durability and accessibility for younger students. These refinements have made the product more practical for everyday use in classrooms, allowing teachers to seamlessly integrate it into their lessons.

Participation in PIP 2024 and the future ISBN registration for the adventure book further validate the product's educational value and its potential for wider distribution. As the project moves forward, the trial at selected schools will provide invaluable feedback that will help refine the product even further. The early results indicate that the kit could foster a deeper understanding of environmental science while promoting critical thinking and problem-solving skills in students. Ultimately, this project serves as a model for how innovative educational tools can address curriculum gaps and enhance student engagement. The "Soil Detectives Adventure Kit" has proven to be a valuable resource for teachers and students alike, and with continued development and wider adoption, it has the potential to make a significant impact in science education.

The "Soil Detectives Adventure Kit" has strong potential for commercialization due to its unique approach to hands-on learning and alignment with the increasing demand for interactive STEM

educational tools. The kit's adventure-based, engaging format makes it an attractive option for pre-school and primary schools looking to enhance their science curriculum with practical, real-world applications. As environmental education becomes a growing priority, the demand for such tools is expected to rise, creating a timely opportunity for the kit to enter the market.

The product's design, especially with its durable gable box format and the accompanying adventure book (with an ISBN), makes it scalable for mass production and distribution. This scalability enables the kit to be easily replicated and distributed to schools, educational publishers, and science education programs on a larger scale. Additionally, the kit's target audience includes not only schools but also homeschooling families, after-school programs, and educational workshops, making it suitable for a wide range of educational settings. Its interactive nature also aligns with current trends in education that emphasize inquiry-based learning and critical thinking.

Partnership opportunities with educational publishers, curriculum developers, and government agencies could help expand the kit's reach. Licensing the kit to educational publishers for broader distribution could also be a viable commercialization strategy. Overall, the "Soil Detectives Adventure Kit" has the potential to make a significant impact in science education while tapping into a growing market for interactive, STEM-focused learning tools.

5. CONCLUSION

The "Soil Detectives Adventure Kit" successfully addresses key gaps in the science curriculum, particularly the lack of hands-on, practical learning related to soil science. It also helps align learning across primary and secondary levels, ensuring students gain consistent and progressive knowledge in science. The kit's success at the International e-Content Development Competition 2023 and positive feedback from educators and students show its value as an engaging educational tool. The updated version, along with its participation in PIP 2024 and future ISBN registration, demonstrates its readiness for wider use in schools. Initial trials at selected schools confirmed that the kit improves students' understanding of soil science while fostering critical thinking and curiosity. With further development, the "Soil Detectives Adventure Kit" has the potential to become a key resource in science education, helping students apply theoretical knowledge to real-world challenges.

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